
**D-JRP7-1.4 - Report on strain
collection and strategy for
selection of strains for
sequencing.**

JRP7 - LISTADAPT

V1.0 01/09/2019

Responsible Partner: ANSES

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2018
Duration	60 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

JRP Deliverable/Report number	D-JRP7-1.4
Join Integrative/Research Project	JRP7 - LISTADAPT
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Due month of the deliverable	
Actual submission month	24
Type <i>R: Document, report</i> <i>DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.</i> <i>OTHER</i>	
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public</i> <i>CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)</i>	PU

Report on strain collection and strategy for selection of strains for sequencing

1. Strain collections

The LISTADPAT collection is organized in three major compartment (and sub-compartment):

- C1: Environment / farm / animal
- C2: RTE Food
 - o C2-a: RTE fish
 - o C2-b: RTE meat
 - o C2-c: Dairy products
 - o C2-d: Produce (vegetables and fruits)
 - o C2-e: Composite dishes (mixed salads, sandwiches)
- C3: Sporadic human cases

The main focus was on C1 compartment. A large review of existing collections of environmental or animal strains has been carried out. Table 1 summarizes the available collections and the number of strains selected thank to the algorithm developed (see part 2.)

Table 1. List of newly established external collaborations for increasing diversity of LISTADAPT strain collection

Partners	Country	Contact	Strain collection panel	Number of selected strains*
University of Helsinki	Finland	Dr Miia Lindstrom	animal sector (cattle and farm strains)	180 strains
BIOR The Institute of Food Safety, Animal Health and Environment	Latvia	Dr Zanete Steingolde	animal sector (cattle and farm strains)	36 strains
Faculty of Food Science and Fisheries - West Pomeranian University of Technology	Poland	Dr Barbara Szymczak	Environment (soil, fruits, vegetables)	80 strains
PIWET	Poland	Dr Wasyl Dariusz	Environment/farm/animal	To contact again in 2019
ONCFS	France	Dr. Anouk Decors	Wild animal	Discussion in progress
University of Munich	Germany	Dr Verena Hohenester	Wild animal	32 strains
Neiker Tecnalia	Spain	Dr Ana Hurtado	Farm animal (cattle, sheep)	38 strains

Teagasc	Ireland	Dr Kieran Jordan	animal sector (milk strains)	To contact again in 2019
PHE	UK	Dr Corinne Amar	Wild animal	5 strains
INIAV Animal Pathology Laboratory	Portugal	Dr Leonor Orge	Farm animal (cattle, sheep, poultry)	Selection in progress
Slovenian LNR for Lm	Slovenia	Dr Bojan Paptic	Farm animal (cattle, sheep)	25 strains
NVWA - NL LNR for Lm	The Netherland	Dr Nathalie Loeke	Farm animal	21 strains
Veterinary and Food Laboratory	Estonia	Toomas Kramarenko	Farm animal	Selection in progress

* Selection procedure based on method described below

Figure 1. illustrates the location of the different collection.

7 consortium partners

- AGES (AT)
- VRI (CZ)
- INRA (FR)
- NVI (NO)
- ANSES (FR)
- IZSAM (IT)
- SVA (SE)

15 external partners

- VetSuisse (CH)
- Munich University (DE)
- Freie Universität of Berlin IHMT (DE)
- VetLab (EE)
- NEIKER (ES)
- University of Helsinki (FI)
- French Institute for Pig Industry (FR)
- Veterinary faculty of Zagreb (HR)
- BIOR (LT)
- VWA (NL)
- Szczecin University (PL)
- INIAV (PT)
- Veterinary faculty of Ljubjana (SI)
- Public Health England (UK)

- Consortium partners
- External partners
- Possible collaboration

17 countries
22 partners

1341 strains -> 947 from animals, 354 from soil & environment

Figure 1. Location and diversity of the collection available for LISTADAPT C1 compartment.

2. Strategy for selection of strains for sequencing

Sampling is crucial for the pertinence/performance of the genomic analysis carried out. Several strategies of sampling are available and the analyst must adapt to the global objective he has. At least two different strategies can be envisaged. If the objective is to characterize the strains that contribute the more to consumer exposure, the sampling effort must be put on strains isolated in the food product from the main food companies (or issued from the main food producing regions). Stratified sampling if commonly applied is such situations. If the objective is to explore the diversity of strains

circulating in a country, the analyst can use the metadata associated to strain to reach that objective. When there is more than two categories of metadata describing the strains, the selection requires an algorithm of selection

A three steps process for selecting strains based on metadata information (e.g. region, type of animal,...) is originally proposed. This method relies on the Gower's coefficient (1971), which is a metric expressing a dissimilarity: the “distance” between two units is the sum of all the variable-specific distances (associated to metadata categories). GC metric is capable of combining numeric and categorical data. GC offers the opportunity to the analyst to select weights for each individual variable, effectively altering the importance of each metadata categories (region more important than year). A three-step process is proposed:

- calculating dissimilarity matrix based on Gower distance
- applying the clustering method on dissimilarity matrix with hierarchical clustering. (agglomerative (bottom-up approach of clustering))
- assessing clusters with the “Silhouette” method: the silhouette plot displays a measure of how close each point in one cluster is to points in the neighboring clusters.

The approach is illustrated in Figure below. An rscript (strain_metaselect.r) is available (<https://github.com/lguillier/LISTADAPT>). It takes a csv file that includes strains ID and metadata information. It provides as output a csv file of selected strains.

Figure 2. Method for selecting LISTADAPT strains based on their metadata for diversity characterization.

